

ANCIENT TRADITIONS, CRAFTS ARE DEVELOPING.

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Annotation: Fergana is one of the oldest and richest countries in Uzbek cotton growing. At present, cotton textile clusters in the region serve to revitalize the cotton industry. This article shows the development of handicrafts in our country, as well as in the city of Fergana.

Keywords: Neighborhood, textile clusters, cotton, trade, women, gender equality

Fergana is one of the oldest and richest countries in Uzbek cotton growing. At present, cotton textile clusters in the region serve to revitalize the cotton industry. The use of a cluster system is an example of how huge changes can be made in cotton production. According to scientists, in the past, a kilogram of cotton fiber was sold for 1-1.5 dollars. At present, a kilogram of cotton fiber is sold by cluster enterprises for \$ 25-30. This is proof that cotton growing is becoming one of the most profitable sectors of our economy. In general, Fergana has long been one of the largest industrial centers of the country. It is unique not only to cities and villages. In Dehkanabad mahalla of Buvayda district, the main part of the population has been engaged in blacksmithing for centuries. More than 300 people in the neighborhood have taken up the profession. They make everything from fishing boats to medical equipment. It is in this field that we can see the activity of women. Of course, when we say broom, we mean something insignificant. But it has its own masters. These are, of course, the hard work of our women. There are many who are working hard to develop the economy in the interests of the country.

In this regard, exemplary work is being carried out, especially in Rishtan district. Of course, the world is amazed by the mastery of potters from the ordinary soil of the city. As a result of the work on the development of handicrafts and

entrepreneurship, the range of products is growing and exports are growing. More than 70 young women work at the R-Koron enterprise in the city. Ceramic trays with a height of 2 meters 22 centimeters and a weight of 81 kilograms, with a capacity of 40 kilograms of pilaf at a time, amaze foreigners. Marhabo Polvonova, the head of the Zar Kulol Rishtan family enterprise in Rishtan district, the owner of the Order of Labor Glory, came to this conclusion. In 2016, we started a family business in Zar Kulol Rishtan. our work went on.¹⁴ We recruited local youth.

A YEAR LATER, OUR POTTERY PRODUCTS WERE DEMANDED IN THE DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN MARKETS. In 2020, we sold \$ 40,000 worth of products to Kyrgyzstan. We are gaining strength from the practical work of our government to support entrepreneurs. We are conducting research to increase the range of products, improve quality, reduce costs. In particular, we pay attention to the use of gas-efficient, alternative energy stoves. Our products are delivered to Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Jizzakh, Bukhara regions. I am proud to have a small share in this country, in the new life of New Uzbekistan. The doors of opportunity are opening. We, the entrepreneurs, feel it every day in our lives. It is enough to act as a team with honest work. while famous for its schools of wood carving and painting, Rishtan has long been known around the world for its ceramic art. Therefore, Rishtan ceramics are in demand in foreign markets. It is gratifying that during the pandemic, the International Ceramics Center was established in the district to help people stay at home, engage in handicrafts and earn money. Uzbekistan is a favorable country for travel and pilgrimage tourism. The industrial city of Angren attracts tourists from the villages of Yangiabad and Lashkerak. Many hotels and guest houses are waiting for tourists. Food and service outlets are being built. As we drove along the Dukent River from the city of Angren, a smooth and smooth road took us to the New Fortress. and an entrepreneur with guest houses. Thanks to a loan from the state, Aisha takes her sisters and serves them as tourists. Because of my interest in entrepreneurship, I tried myself in the field of tourism. At the moment, we have 3 hotels and a family guest house. Tomini yo The pandemic

has affected all sectors, especially tourism. If the situation improves, there is no doubt that Angren will become a favorite destination for foreign tourists. The boxing federation of Uzbekistan is located in the Yangiabad fortress, where athletes hold training camps. In recent years, there is a growing focus on women in society. Gender equality, improving working and living conditions for women and the full realization of their educational potential. The importance of women in society is growing.

As a result of the priority given to gender equality in the country at the initiative of the President, ensuring the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of women, strengthening their role in state and public life has become one of the priorities of state policy. We are all proud of the fact that the reforms being carried out in our country in this direction are recognized at the international level. In this regard, Uzbekistan ranks 45th in the world. In this sense, our country has surpassed more than 130 PI (Inter-Parliamentary Union) member states, including Germany, Australia, Canada, the United States and Central Asia. included in the list of states that are part of the government. It should be noted that the work of the Commission on Gender Equality, chaired by the Senate Speaker Tanzila Norbaeva, is highly appreciated by foreign partners. Of course, these achievements are the result of the noble work carried out in our country to protect human interests, build an open civil society and a democratic state. It is noteworthy that the Strategy for Achieving Gender Equality, approved in Uzbekistan, is the first normative document developed and adopted at the initiative of the parliament. As a result of these reforms, for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached the level set by the UN, and according to this indicator it is among the TOP-50 countries (women in parliament) by almost 32%. rose to 37th place among 190 parliaments in the world. The share of women in management positions has increased to 27%. (6 women governors, 1 ambassador). Today, more than 15,000 advanced, leading, educated women are formed in ministries and departments. In order to work with women, "Women's Notebooks" were introduced.

Kokand is the tourism capital of the Turkic Council. We dreamed of holding international festivals in different parts of the country, such as silk and spices, and international festivals of baxshi. Kokand has been described as a city of world craftsmen. Every two years, a festival is held in our city, and we present our intentions to the world.

List of used literature

1. New Uzbekistan newspaper, issues of 2021.
2. Kamilova F. Hotel and restaurant tourism. T. Teacher.2002
3. Nurmatov M, Ismoilov I, Chorjeva Z. "Fergana Valley Tourism and National Crafts Center". Abstracts of the scientific conference. Samdu 2002 pp. 103-105